

Teaching with φ -3PO: An AI-Tutor System for Enhanced Learning

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Abstract

The increase in educational attainment worldwide comes with demands for novel tools to be used by students and teachers. Language models provide a great opportunity in this respect, but the technology must be handled carefully. To facilitate the adoption of language models in this key domain, we design multiple extensions of a model from the Phi-3 family, originally developed by Microsoft. We call the collection of our extensions φ -3PO. We fine-tune Phi-3 using DPO on a carefully curated list of datasets, including data from the students taking the MNL course. We apply two techniques to further fine-tune the model to improve its performance on multiple-choice questions, including Chain-of-Thought prompting and Supervised Fine-Tuning. We compress the model using the GPTQ quantization technique. The 8-bit version of the model retains the original performance while halving the size. We also design a RAG system by gathering a collection of STEM-related factual data and employing a state-of-the-art embedding model. We implement two systems for embedding lookup, using naive search and a FAISS index. RAG is shown to be effective on knowledge domains which were included in the pre-selected data. Overall, our models consistently perform well on the tasks they were designed for.

1 Introduction

As the number of students pursuing higher education in Switzerland¹ and worldwide² increases, the educational system has to adapt to higher throughput. *Large language models (LLM)* are among the tools waiting to be adopted by educators to provide personalized support for students, and for students pursuing independent learning (Kasneci et al., 2023).

In spite of their appeal, LLMs need work to be adapted to educational purposes. LLMs require

¹<https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/en/home/statistics/education-science/pupils-students.gnpdetail.2024-0155.html>

²https://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/f_unesco1015_brochure_web_en.pdf

careful fine-tuning to make them into helpful assistants (Ouyang et al., 2022). The models also consume significant computational resources at training and inference time, which leaves a deep carbon footprint (Luccioni et al., 2023). Last but not least, LLMs tend to produce hallucinations (Huang et al., 2023), including making up or incorrectly recalling facts. This feature significantly limits their adoption as educational tools: if a pupil has to cross-check the information provided by the LLM, why asking it in the first place?

In this project, we developed an educational assistant LLM with a focus on the the courses from EPFL. We call our assistant φ -3PO, short for “Preference-optimized Phi-3”. We explored multiple approaches to make it helpful in answering open-ended and multiple-choice questions, including DPO (Rafailov et al., 2023) and supervised fine-tuning. We addressed the costs of inference and storage with a quantized version of our assistant, with up to $4.2\times$ compression. We also explored *Resource-Augmented Generation (RAG)* as a way of dealing with hallucinations. RAG allows the model to utilize an external database with efficient lookup to aid generation.

Our work is based on *Phi-3* (Abdin et al., 2024), a modern family of LLMs developed by Microsoft. The original Phi-3 already achieves impressive results, comparable in performance with models twice as large. We further improve their performance by fine-tuning on a carefully curated selection of datasets. Our analysis demonstrates improvements on the widely-used MMLU benchmark (Hendrycks et al., 2021). Quantization shows only moderate performance drops, with the 8-bit model effectively halving the size of the original model without noticeable decrease in performance. Finally, our results on RAG demonstrate that the model learns to better answer questions on the topics that were provided to it in the external database. Overall, we believe that our model and its extensions demonstrate highly competitive performance given a relatively modest size of 3.8B parameters.

2 Related Work

The potential of LLMs as personalized assistants was first introduced using a technique called Reinforcement learning from human feedback (Ouyang et al., 2022). It demonstrated impressive results, but it requires careful tuning to reach good performance (Huang et al., 2024). We rely on a comparable and far simpler method, Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) (Rafailov et al., 2023), which fine-tunes language models using preference data collected from human raters, aiming to generate outputs that better match human preferences. There are two main approaches to enhance task-specific abilities in LLMs further: supervised fine-tuning (Sun et al., 2019) and in-context learning (also known as few-shot) (Mann et al., 2020). In addition to DPO, we experiment with both of these methods and demonstrate their effectiveness in the educational domain. Another prompting method that has gained popularity recently is Chain of Thought (CoT) (Wei et al., 2023), where an LLM leverages step-by-step reasoning to enhance performance on complex tasks. CoT can be combined with the other methods mentioned here. Motivated by recent advances in this area, such as MMLU-Pro (Wang et al., 2024), we developed a novel dataset to further explore CoT capabilities.

LLMs are already beginning to be adopted for educational purposes. Duolingo, the leading platform for online language learning, is running a pilot program to integrate GPT-4 for explaining answers and live conversations³. Khan academy is also integrating a personalized LLM-tutor⁴. Kasneci et al. discuss the opportunities and risks of language models in this domain in detail. They show that LLMs can be helpful through the entire education vertical, from primary school (Abdelghani et al., 2023) to university-level courses (Bhat et al., 2022). At the same time, the challenges of introducing LLMs in this domain include, apart from the aforementioned hallucinations, cheating with the use of these new tools (Cotton et al., 2024).

3 Approach

For our AI tutoring system, we leveraged the Phi-3 mini model (Abdin et al., 2024), a 3.8B parameter model developed by Microsoft. The Phi-3 mini model is known for its ability to achieve decent performance despite its relatively small size. This impressive performance is attributed to the approach used in pre-training the model, which

involved high quality, heavily filtered web and synthetic data. The final system is illustrated in Figure 1 and it is explained in detail in the following subsections.

Preference data collection. We collected preference data to adapt the Phi-3 mini model for our specific task of answering multiple-choice questions in the context of AI tutoring for EPFL courses. We were given a comprehensive set of questions from various EPFL courses covering STEM-related topics: mathematics, physics, computer science and electrical engineering. Using GPT-3.5 (Brown et al., 2020) we generated two distinct answers for each question, designed to exhibit different levels of quality. All team members used chain-of-thought techniques, particularly relying on "Let's think step-by-step" and "Explain your answer in detail by going through each option.". One notable improvement in answer generation was providing the correct answer alongside the question and prompting the chatbot to explain its reasoning. Conversely, when withholding the answer, responses tended to be lower in quality, albeit still acceptable. While generating responses with GPT-3.5, we engaged in a conversational feedback loop, iteratively refining the answers by providing feedback to GPT-3.5's initial outputs to shape the responses to be diverse, similar in quality and sufficiently complex. The most common system-instruction that we used is available in the Appendix A.1. We then evaluated these answer pairs by conducting a thorough assessment of each pair, judging them based on multiple criteria. Through this evaluation process we identified the preferred and rejected responses for each question pair, selecting the answer that was superior overall as preferred.

DPO Model. To align the base Phi-3 mini model with human preferences, we employed DPO as described by (Rafailov et al., 2023). We started with the pretrained Phi-3 mini model, which had been trained on a large corpus of text data. This pretrained model served as our reference policy π_{ref} . We prepared the human preference data collected with pairs of responses to the same prompt, where human annotators indicated their preferred response y_w over the rejected one y_l given a prompt x . This yielded a dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(x, y_w, y_l)\}$.

The core of the DPO method is the binary cross-entropy loss function, which implicitly optimizes the model's policy to align with human preferences. The loss function is derived under the Bradley-Terry model. It assumes that given the rewards r_1 and r_2 of outputs y_1 and y_2

³<https://blog.duolingo.com/duolingo-max/>

⁴<https://www.khanmigo.ai/>

Figure 1: An overview of the techniques we employed to develop various versions of φ -3PO starting from Phi-3: *fine-tuning on MCQA data, quantization and retrieval-augmented generation.*

respectively, the probability of preferring y_1 to y_2 is $p(y_1 \succ y_2) = \exp r_1 / (\exp r_1 + \exp r_2)$. Rafailov et al. then derive that a policy π^* , that is maximizing the rewards under a KL-divergence constraint with π_{ref} , would satisfy

$$p^*(y_w \succ y_l | x) = \sigma \left(\beta \left(\log \frac{\pi^*(y_w|x)}{\pi_{ref}(y_w|x)} - \log \frac{\pi^*(y_l|x)}{\pi_{ref}(y_l|x)} \right) \right),$$

where σ denotes the sigmoid function, and β is a hyperparameter controlling the strength of preference weighting. We optimized the model parameters θ to maximize the likelihood of the preferred responses using the following loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}_{DPO}(\pi_\theta; \pi_{ref}) = -\mathbb{E}_{(x, y_w, y_l) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\log \sigma \left(\beta \left(\log \frac{\pi_\theta(y_w|x)}{\pi_{ref}(y_w|x)} - \log \frac{\pi_\theta(y_l|x)}{\pi_{ref}(y_l|x)} \right) \right) \right]$$

This objective function dynamically adjusts the model’s output probabilities to increase the likelihood of generating preferred responses over non-preferred ones.

Final System. Following the development of our DPO model π_θ , we adapted our model, using data specifically designed for the task of multiple-choice question answering (MCQA). To achieve this, we employ two fine-tuning approaches.

Firstly, we utilized supervised fine-tuning (SFT) to adapt our model to MCQA. We trained our model on a dataset consisting of multiple-choice questions, where each input is paired with the correct option’s single letter as ground truth. This process enabled our model (later referred to as Phi-3 SFT single-letter) to shift from providing answer-by-reasoning responses to outputting only the sin-

gle correct letter, resulting in the π_{mcqa} MCQA model.

As a second method, we fine-tuned our model (later referred to as Phi-3 SFT reasoning) using our own crafted CoT dataset. For each question, we provided ground truth in the form of step-by-step explanations and the correct options’ letter at the end. This allowed us to leverage CoT to generate answers while teaching the model the correct format for extracting the output letter.

To further facilitate both fine-tuning methods, we employed few-shot prompting. In this approach, we presented our model with several example questions and their corresponding answers in the desired style, designed specifically for each method. More specifically, we provided prompts that showcased single letter answer for the first approach, and step-by-step explanations for CoT approach. This led our model to align with the desired system, facilitating post-processing and simplifying the extraction of the option letter produced by the model. The prompts used in our final system are provided in the Appendix A.6.

Overall, we found that the first method with few-shot prompting delivered best results, so we did not use CoT in the final model. For its answer extraction, we use the next token output probabilities from the model and select the answer as the choice (A, B, C, D) with the highest probability.

RAG. Language models are prone to hallucinations and inaccurate recall of information (Huang et al., 2023). This tendency is inevitable given the limited capacity of the model’s weights to store information. A simple fix to this problem comes

by attaching an external storage of information to the language model. RAG was implemented using dense lookup of facts in a database of short texts (“facts”). For each fact, we pre-compute its embeddings using the GTE embedding model (Li et al., 2023) and store them in a local database. GTE is a general-purpose text embedding model trained with multi-stage contrastive learning. It was trained so that semantically similar texts will produce embeddings that are close in terms of cosine similarity. Hence, when querying, we embed the question too, and look up the top-3 facts in the database that are most similar based on cosine similarity. The facts are then appended to the prompt together with the question.

Quantization. As a further augmentation, we quantized our model using the Post-Training Quantization (PTQ) method with the GPTQ algorithm (Frantar et al., 2022). For every layer ℓ in the network, we aim to find a quantized version \widehat{W}_ℓ of the original weights W_ℓ . This is known as the layer-wise compression problem, which aims to minimize performance degradation by ensuring that the outputs ($\widehat{W}_\ell X_\ell$) of these new weights are as close as possible to the original outputs ($W_\ell X_\ell$). Mathematically, this can be expressed as:

$$\underset{\widehat{W}_\ell}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\| W_\ell X_\ell - \widehat{W}_\ell X_\ell \right\|_2^2$$

The GPTQ algorithm solves the quantization problem by iteratively selecting and quantizing weights in a fixed order for all rows of a matrix, regardless of the individual weights’ impact on error. This strategy accelerates computation, as some operations need to be performed only once for each column, rather than once for each weight. Additionally, GPTQ employs a Cholesky decomposition⁵ to address numerical inaccuracies that arise when scaling up to very large models, which aligns with our approach of using a >3B model. We experiment with 3-bit, 4-bit, and 8-bit quantization to find the optimal trade-off between performance and compression, where we demonstrate that the 8-bit quantization does decrease the performance. Moreover, we use our MMLU as calibration data to retain maximum performance for our final task of MCQA.

4 Experiments

In this section, we outline the experimental setup of our work, including the data sources, evalua-

tion methods, and baselines. We also discuss the experimental details and present the results and findings.

4.1 Data

DPO Datasets. To train our DPO model, we used three distinct datasets.

EPFL Preference Dataset. This dataset consists of preference pairs collected with the GPT Wrapper package by students enrolled in the CS-552 course. The dataset includes 1522 unique questions, each featuring multiple preference pairs ranked by the students on various ranking criteria. We determined the chosen and rejected answer for each preference pair of every question based on the ‘overall’ ranking. This resulted in more than 20,000 entries, each comprising a question with a rejected and chosen answer. We decided to focus exclusively on the ‘overall’ ranking since we found it to be a more consistent and reliable measure of preference compared to individual criteria, which can vary significantly between raters due to their subjective nature. The overall ranking reflects the user’s combined opinion on all other criteria, which aligns with our end goal of predicting outcomes that best meet user preferences.

Stack Exchange (Team, 2021). This dataset includes questions along with their most upvoted and most downvoted answers from the Stack Exchange network, which we use as preference pairs of chosen and rejected answers, respectively. The dataset covers a variety of domains, but we filtered it to contain only subjects that are relevant for this project. More specifically, we focused exclusively on STEM categories, making a total of 54,458 entries. The detailed list of these categories is included in the Appendix A.2.

Ultra Feedback (Bartolome et al., 2023). This dataset comprises prompts from diverse resources, each one with 4 different responses generated by different LLMs. Each response is rated using GPT-4 based on fine-grained criteria including instruction-following, truthfulness, honesty, and helpfulness. We used the already binarized Ultra Feedback dataset⁶ which was obtained by preprocessing the original dataset. During this preprocessing, the response with the highest mean rating out of the four was selected as the chosen answer, and a response with a lower mean was randomly chosen as the rejected answer. The final UltraFeedback dataset consists of 60,917 entries.

⁵https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cholesky_decomposition

⁶<https://huggingface.co/datasets/argilla/ultrafeedback-binarized-preferences>

For all of the above-mentioned datasets we removed entries where both the chosen and the rejected answer were the same to avoid confusing the model. Finally, all datasets were formatted to follow a consistent format and were structured as a JSONL file. Each line in the file represents a single JSON object that includes a *prompt* followed by *chosen* and *rejected* responses.

For constant evaluation across all experiments on our DPO models, we set aside 10% from each of the DPO datasets.

MCQA Datasets. Furthermore, we used additional datasets for the MCQA task. More specifically, we utilized two types of data corresponding to our two approaches to SFT.

For the first approach, as we aimed to restrict the model’s output to a single-letter answer, we used data that included multiple-choice questions, each with provided options and only a corresponding single-letter answer. We processed two specific datasets for this task: the auxiliary train split of the Measuring Massive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU) dataset, which contains a wide variety of multiple-choice questions from various fields, totaling 99,842 entries (Hendrycks et al., 2021), and the train split of the AI2 Reasoning Challenge Dataset (ARC), which consists of 3,370 multiple-choice science exam questions (Clark et al., 2018). These datasets are well-suited for our goal of developing a real-world LM for educational assistance in the context of MCQA, as they consist of STEM-related questions with precisely four answer choices, one of which is correct. After preprocessing, each entry in the dataset was formatted as follows: `{"subject": <subject>, "question": "Question: <question> Options: <options> Answer:", "answer": <answer>}`

In our second approach, we aimed to enhance our model’s performance by providing it with reasons for each answer, rather than just the correct letter. To achieve this, we created a novel dataset by selecting 96 questions from the MMLU auxiliary train split and augmenting each sample with a *reasoning* field generated by our DPO model. To create the reasoning for each question, we experimented with various prompts to guide the model toward the desired output. We identified the most effective prompt for generating our final data to be: *Question:[question] Options:[options] Answer:[answer]. Explain why [answer] is the correct answer, step by step by reasoning through each option. At the end of your reasoning provide the correct option and end strictly with: “The correct option is: [answer]”*

To ensure consistent evaluation throughout all experiments on our MCQA models, we used the separate test set from both MMLU and ARC datasets, consisting of 14,042 and 3,548 samples, respectively.

RAG. For the RAG component of our model, we collected documents from four datasets available on HuggingFace, focusing specifically on STEM fields. The documents include *ayoubkirouane/arxiv-physics*⁷, consisting of 30,000 questions and answers related to physics sourced from the ArXiv repository; *legacy-datasets/wikipedia*⁸, filtered to include only STEM-related entries; *AlaaElhilo/Wikipedia_ComputerScience*⁹, featuring 7600 Wikipedia facts focused on computer science topics; and *ArtifactAI/arxiv-cs-ml-instruct-tune-50k*¹⁰, which consists of 50,000 question-answer pairs derived from CS/ML related ArXiv abstracts.

Quantization. To retain maximum MCQA performance, we calibrate the quantization using 5,000 question-answer pairs from the auxiliary train split of the MMLU dataset.

All mentioned datasets are publicly available and were utilized in accordance with their respective data usage policies.

4.2 Evaluation method

DPO Model. To assess the performance of our DPO models, a set of quantitative evaluation metrics were employed. We consider accuracy as a fundamental metric, alongside loss and margins. Accuracy measures the percentage of instances where the model assigns higher rewards to the chosen sample than to the rejected one. Margins represent the mean difference between the chosen and corresponding rejected rewards. As mentioned in the Data section, these metrics were calculated on our held out DPO validation set, consisting of 10% from each of the DPO datasets.

Furthermore, to evaluate the overall generative ability of our final DPO model, we utilized MT-Bench (Zheng et al., 2024). MT-Bench employs a hybrid approach, using both qualitative and quantitative measures to assess LLMs. It evaluates LLMs using GPT-4 as a judge, through multi-turn conversations, focusing on their ability to engage in

⁷<https://huggingface.co/datasets/ayoubkirouane/arxiv-physics>

⁸<https://huggingface.co/datasets/legacy-datasets/wikipedia>

⁹https://huggingface.co/datasets/AlaaElhilo/Wikipedia_ComputerScience

¹⁰<https://huggingface.co/datasets/ArtifactAI/arxiv-cs-ml-instruct-tune-50k>

coherent and engaging exchanges. Specifically, we used the single-answer grading strategy from the benchmark. Single-answer grading is a mode in which GPT-4 evaluates responses from LLM, directly assigning a score to each individual answer. This evaluation process involves two phases: initially, the language model generates a response to a prompt, and subsequently, it provides a second response to the same prompt under slightly altered conditions to test consistency and robustness. For simplicity, we use the average from both phases. The prompts for GPT-4 to act as a judge are provided in the Appendix A.3

MCQA Model. To evaluate our MCQA models, we assess their accuracy, which measures the percentage of questions where the model’s selected answer matches the correct answer out of the four options. To ensure consistent evaluation for the experiments, we use MMLU and ARC test sets.

RAG. Our RAG model is evaluated using accuracy as in MCQA, with the expectation of improving the score of the final MCQA model.

Quantization. We evaluate our quantized models by their accuracy on MMLU and ARC test sets, as well as by comparing their size and GPU memory usage. GPU memory usage is determined by calculating the maximum memory utilized during inference with max token size of 128 and batch size of 1. To assess quantization efficiency, we introduce our own quantitative metric taking into account both the models accuracy and size, relative to the non-quantized model. The formula to evaluate each quantized model based on balancing accuracy loss and model size reduction is given by:

$$\text{Score} = (1 - \Delta\text{Acc}) \cdot w_{\text{acc}} + \Delta\text{Size} \cdot w_{\text{size}}$$

where w_{acc} and w_{size} are the weights assigned to the accuracy loss and size reduction components of the score, respectively,

$$\Delta\text{Acc} = \frac{\text{Avg. Acc. of Non-quantized} - \text{Avg. Acc. of Quantized}}{\text{Avg. Acc. of Non-quantized}}$$

represents the normalized accuracy loss, and

$$\Delta\text{Size} = \frac{\text{Size of Non-quantized} - \text{Size of Quantized}}{\text{Size of Non-quantized}}$$

represents the normalized size reduction. As our goal is to retain maximum possible accuracy while significantly reducing the model size, we assign weight values w_{acc} of 0.7 and w_{size} of 0.3 in the trade-off score calculation.

4.3 Baselines

To rigorously assess the performance of our models, we conducted comparisons with several SOTA

chatbots.

DPO. For our final DPO Model, we used MT-bench in single-answer grading mode. Our baselines included GPT-4, GPT-3.5 Turbo (Achiam et al., 2023), Claude v1 (Anthropic, 2024), Vicuna 33B v1.3 (Chiang et al., 2023), Llama 2 70B Chat, and Llama 2 7B Chat (Touvron et al., 2023).

MCQA. For the final MCQA capabilities we compared our model against three baselines, including Llama-3 8B, Phi-3-mini-4k-instruct and GPT-3.5 Turbo.

RAG. Our RAG model was evaluated against the base model (final MCQA) to quantify improvements in integrating external knowledge bases during answer generation

Quantization. The impact of model quantization was assessed by comparing the quantized version of our model with the non-quantized basel (final MCQA).

4.4 Experimental details

DPO Model. Our alignment training approach leverages LoRA adapters (Hu et al., 2021), fine-tuning our Phi-3-mini model efficiently. We used a β value of 0.1, in line with the official DPO paper. We used AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of $5e-5$ and a linear scheduler to stabilize training. The model was trained with batch size of 1 across three epochs and enabled *FP16* training to leverage faster computations and reduce memory usage. The LoRA configuration includes alpha set at 16, the rank of the update matrices (r) set at 32, and a dropout of 0.1. The max length was set to 512 for the chosen and the rejected answer, and 128 for the prompt. The training using all three DPO datasets took 60 hours on a single Tesla V100 32GB GPU.

MCQA Model. We applied SFT on top of our final DPO model. For our SFT models we also used LoRA adapters, with alpha set at 32, the rank of the update matrices (r) set at 64, and a dropout of 0.1. We used AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of $5e-5$ and a linear scheduler, using a batch size of 8, across 3 epochs. Max sequence length of 256 was used. The training lasted 7 hours on a single Tesla V100 32GB GPU.

RAG. For each fact in the documents, we pre-compute its embeddings using the gte-large-en-v1.5 model¹¹ and store them locally. To answer a given question, we first compute its embedding, and then look up the top-3 facts in the database based on cosine similarity

¹¹<https://huggingface.co/Alibaba-NLP/gte-large-en-v1.5>

(Naive method). Additionally, to explore different retrieval efficiencies, we employed Faiss IndexFlatL2 (Douze et al., 2024) as an alternative search mechanism. This approach utilizes Euclidean distance for fact retrieval, thus, enabling a comparative analysis with the cosine similarity-based dense lookup to determine the optimal search strategy for enhancing retrieved fact relevance. The maximum fact length is set to 256. We omit facts that have cosine similarity less than 0.7. The fact is appended to the question using the LLamaIndex prompt template¹². The RAG has a latency of 0.76 and 2.82 seconds per sample with Naive and Faiss retrieval, respectively, using Tesla V100 32GB GPU. Contrary to our expectations, FAISS actually provides slower lookup compared to dense search. However, in our case we can put the entire database into RAM, while FAISS was designed for the case where this would not be possible.

Quantization. We applied GPTQ quantization (Frantar et al., 2022), experimenting with three different bit-widths: 3, 4, and 8-bit. We configured the group size to 128 and set the act order to *False*, which dictates that columns should not be quantized in order to decrease activation size. Each quantization process took approximately 30 minutes using the same Tesla V100 32GB GPU.

4.5 Results

DPO Model. From Table 1 we can see the results for the different data combinations. As expected, training on all datasets yielded the highest validation accuracy of 0.8336, lowest validation loss of 0.476, and highest validation margins of 4.311. Since the results suggest that the model trained on all three datasets generalizes the best, we chose it as our final DPO model.

Model	Score
GPT-4	8.99
Phi-3 Mini DPO	8.20
GPT-3.5 Turbo	7.94
Claude v1	7.90
Vicuna 33B v1.3	7.12
Llama 2 70B Chat	6.85

Table 2: The breakdown of LLMs’ MT-bench scores in the average from 1st and 2nd turn of a dialogue. The score is assigned by GPT-4 and the max is 10.

Furthermore, to evaluate the overall generative ability of our final model we present Table 2, which shows MT-Bench leaderboard based on single-answer grading with GPT-4. Our model scores 8.2,

¹²https://docs.llamaindex.ai/en/stable/module_guides/models/prompts/

outperforming most of the baselines. This suggests that our model is highly capable of responding in a way that humans prefer.

MCQA Model. Table 3 shows the results of two SFT model variants alongside the base DPO model without SFT modifications, across three different few-shot settings. As expected, increasing the number of shots enhances overall performance. Both SFT models significantly improved upon the base DPO model’s performance across both datasets. The best result was achieved with the SFT for a single letter, which was anticipated due to this model’s consistent adherence to the prompt template that requires outputting a single letter. Furthermore, the SFT for a single letter was trained on a large dataset, whereas the SFT model with reasoning was exposed to far fewer samples. To better assess the quality of our model, we also compared it with the baselines presented in Table 4.

Model	MMLU
GPT-3.5 Turbo (5-shot)	0.7000
Phi-3-SFT single-letter (3-shot)	0.6852
Phi-3-mini-4k-instruct (3-shot)	0.6840
LLama 8B (5-shot)	0.6840

Table 4: Performance of our model (in bold) on MMLU relative to (self-reported) results of the baseline models.

Quantization. Table 5 presents the evaluation results for three quantized models alongside the non-quantized baseline. Each quantized model significantly reduces both size and GPU memory usage with minimal impact on performance. Among the quantized models, the 4-bit version stands out with a trade-off score of 0.899, demonstrating the best balance between a reduced memory footprint and a small performance drop. The 4-bit model achieves an average accuracy drop of only 1.35 percentage points from the non-quantized model while reducing the model size by 70.3%. Another impressive result is observed with the 8-bit version, which almost completely preserves the original accuracy. This shows that even though we converted higher precision weight values into lower precision versions, the model still retains a high level of performance.

RAG. Table 6 compares the performance of two RAG search mechanisms —Naive and Faiss—against our non-augmented baseline in a 3-shot setting. The Naive mechanism outperforms both the Faiss and the baseline, demonstrating improved accuracy on both datasets. This improvement shows RAG’s capability to leverage relevant facts to enhance the models’ performance. Such an example can be found in the Appendix A.5.

EPFL Dataset	UltraFeedback	Stack Exchange	Accuracy \uparrow	Loss \downarrow	Margins \uparrow
✓			0.5500	0.696	1.886
✓	✓		0.7547	0.624	2.532
✓		✓	0.7906	0.516	3.548
✓	✓	✓	0.8336	0.476	4.311

Table 1: Performance of DPO Trained Phi-3 Mini Model with different training dataset combinations.

Model	0 - shot		1 - shot		3 - shot	
	ARC	MMLU	ARC	MMLU	ARC	MMLU
Phi-3-DPO	0.8851	0.6622	0.8886	0.6735	0.8926	0.6801
Phi-3-SFT single-letter	0.8899	0.6719	0.8850	0.6740	0.8943	0.6852
Phi-3-SFT reasoning	0.8911	0.6750	0.8901	0.6735	0.8934	0.6840

Table 3: A comparison of various training and prompting techniques on standard LLM benchmarks.

Model	ARC	MMLU
RAG - Naive	0.8969	0.6885
RAG - Faiss	0.8841	0.6870
Non-augmented model	0.8943	0.6852

Table 6: Comparative performance of RAG using Naive and Faiss search mechanisms in a 3-shot setting.

5 Analysis

DPO performance per Subject. To further assess our final DPO model’s capabilities, we were interested in seeing its fine-grained performance, even more so than the aggregated overall score. This interest stems from the fact that our final DPO model is aligned on datasets mainly consisting of STEM questions. We present the comparison of 4 baseline LLMs regarding their abilities in 8 categories is shown in Figure 2. Overall, our final DPO model demonstrates strong performance across all categories, close to that of GPT-3.5 Turbo. Its STEM score of 9.8, is higher than GPT-4’s, which shows that the model is highly capable for queries from this domain, which makes it a suitable choice for the final goal of AI-tutor for STEM-related topics.

Figure 2: Comparison of our DPO model against 3 state of the art models on the MT-Bench across 8 categories.

RAG performance per Subject. As mentioned in the results section, RAG improves the overall accuracy of the model. However, as our aim is to develop an AI tutor specialized in course content at EPFL, we focused on measuring performance for specific subjects. From Table 7, we can see improvements in subjects like machine learning, electrical engineering, computer science and physics which are key areas of EPFL’s curriculum. This suggests that the documents used for the RAG model, which specifically cover these topics, have proven to be useful. On the other hand, subjects such as biology and chemistry, experienced decreased accuracies, potentially due to noise from unrelated data. This indicates that the RAG model offers enhanced performance in areas relevant to our specialized educational objectives.

Subject	Non-augmented	RAG
<i>machine_learning</i>	0.5803	0.5982
<i>electrical_engineering</i>	0.6137	0.6275
<i>high_school_physics</i>	0.4701	0.4900
<i>college_computer_science</i>	0.5300	0.5400
<i>college_chemistry</i>	0.5400	0.5000
<i>college_biology</i>	0.8402	0.8194

Table 7: Per-subject performance of the base DPO model and its RAG augmented counterpart on MMLU.

6 Ethical considerations

Most applications of LLMs focus on high-resource languages like English, German, and French. As models evolve, there’s a growing push for multilingual capabilities, now supporting around 100 languages. Our model is monolingual, since it was trained on English data only. To make our model multilingual, we propose the use of language-family specific adapters, an approach inspired by

Model	Accuracy (3 - shot)		Model Size (GB)	Max GPU Memory Usage (MB)	Trade-Off Score
	ARC	MMLU			
3-bit	0.8362	0.5768	1.82	2471.24	0.855
4-bit	0.8833	0.6692	2.28	4406.03	0.899
8-bit	0.8934	0.6836	4.11	7901.11	0.838
Non-quantized	0.8943	0.6852	7.67	20574.43	/

Table 5: Comparison of Quantized and Non-Quantized models showing ARC and MMLU 3-shot accuracies, resource footprint, and trade-off scores.

MAD-X (Pfeiffer et al., 2020). For instance, a single adapter could be developed for Slavic family languages, benefiting from their linguistic similarities. This way we can alleviate the curse of multilinguality to some extent and represent the low-resource languages more effectively. This process involves collaboration with native educators for data collection to ensure content relevance, especially in regions that fall behind in progress.

To adapt our tutor for interaction with users through signed languages it could be trained on various datasets, such as the ASL Lexicon Video Dataset for American Sign Language (Athitsos et al., 2008) and the Public DSG Corpus for German Sign Language (Schulder et al., 2021). For sign detection, a suitable architecture designed for spatial-temporal video data could be used. A SOTA pretrained model like SlowFastSign (Ahn et al., 2024), which has demonstrated a minimal word error rate, would be ideal. This model would allow the extraction of sentences or words from the sign language input, which could then serve as inputs to our AI-tutor model.

If the AI tutor works as intended, it offers significant benefits to both students and teachers by providing immediate, accessible answers to queries, on platforms like ED forums where immediate TA engagement may not be feasible. However, there are potential drawbacks, particularly concerning the employment of TAs. At institutions like EPFL, many TAs are international students who rely on these positions for financial support. The automation of answer generation could jeopardize these jobs, disproportionately affecting this vulnerable group who might already face financial challenges. Such an impact could deepen existing inequalities within the academic community. To minimize these adverse effects, it is crucial to position the AI tutor as a complement to, rather than a replacement for, human instructors and TAs.

Apart from the aforementioned implications, cheating facilitated by such an AI tool could also become a significant concern, potentially weaken-

ing the integrity of educational assessments.

Generally, we are confident in the robustness of our model, particularly concerning high ethical concerns such as race and gender, as it demonstrates strong resistance to jailbreaking. No known methods, including forced preambles, have successfully compromised its integrity, examples included in Appendix A.7.

7 Conclusion

In this project, we developed φ -3PO by enhancing the Phi-3 model to create a tuned AI tutor for EPFL’s multiple-choice assessments.

We fine-tune Phi-3 using DPO on a curated list of datasets, including data from the students taking the MNLP course. We apply two techniques to fine-tune the model to improve its performance on MCQA. The implementation of 8-bit GPTQ effectively halved the model size while preserving its original accuracy, showing the feasibility of deploying advanced AI models in resource-constrained environments. Additionally, the integration of the RAG enriched the model’s response quality by leveraging domain-specific databases, which proved especially beneficial in areas covered extensively in the lookup data. Despite these successes, our system has limitations. The effectiveness of RAG is contingent on the relevance and breadth of the external data it accesses, limiting its utility to well-documented domains. Moreover, the specialized nature of our fine-tuning and RAG implementation might not generalize well on all EPFL subjects without additional modifications.

Future work could focus on expanding the model’s application to all EPFL subjects and enlarging RAG documents to cover more diverse fields. This project pushed our boundaries and expanded our knowledge both theoretically and technically. We are thankful for such a challenging project, as it opens new doors and deeply broadens our understanding of the most exciting latest technologies.

8 Contributions

Stefan. DPO Model, Quantization Model, RAG Model, Code handling, Writing

Matea. Datasets processing, MCQA Model, Experiments, Writing

Said. DPO Model, MCQA Model, Experiments, Writing

Mikhail. DPO Model, RAG Model, Code handling, Writing

However, the real contribution was the friends we found along the way.

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A Appendix

A.1 System-Instruction for preference data collection

System Instruction

You are an expert. Please solve the question given by breaking down the problem into simpler steps. Start by understanding the question, then outline each step of your reasoning process clearly before providing the final answer. Give your final answer after step-by-step clear explanation.

A.2 Categories Used from the Stack Exchange Dataset

We filtered the Stack Exchange dataset to include only entries from the following subjects: physics, bioinformatics, electronics, mathoverflow, codereview, cs, cstheory, datascience, matheducators, engineering, ai, cseducators, iot, softwareengineering, stats, networkengineering, scicomp, robotics, devops, astronomy, askubuntu, apple, serverfault, security, webapps and webmasters.

A.3 Single Answer Grading

MT-Bench. The default prompt for single answer grading

[System]
Please act as an impartial judge and evaluate the quality of the response provided by an AI assistant to the user question displayed below. Your evaluation should consider factor such as the helpfulness, relevance, accuracy, depth, creativity, and level of detail of the response. Begin your evaluation by providing a short explanation. Be as objective as possible. After providing your explanation, please rate the response on a scale of 1 to 10 by strictly following this format: "[[rating]]", for example: "Rating: [[5]]".

[Question]
{question}

[Assistant's Answer]
{answer}

A.4 Pairwise Win Rate - Positional Bias.

In the pairwise mode, we directly compared our chosen policy model against the base model, to try and gauge the impact of DPO on aligning model responses. The results show that our Phi-3 Mini DPO recorded 23 wins, 20 losses, and 37 ties against the base model. The comparison is done using GPT-4 as a judge to assess which is the better response, this method is explained in details in the Judging LLM-as-a-judge paper (Zheng et al., 2024). Even though we obtained the results mentioned in the Results section with pairwise-comparison using GPT-4, we decided to investigate this mode further. Since MT-Bench is an expensive toy, and we are a group of students, we decided to reproduce the judging from the official repository¹³, this time using the provided GPT-3.5 API from Milestone 1, instead of GPT-4 (as in the original benchmark). We want to highlight an important pitfall of using this method - the positional bias. To show this we conducted two experiments. First we sampled 200 questions from the given Milestone 2 example dataset. In the initial experiment the first given responses were from the DPO model, while in the second experiment we swapped the positions. With Table 8, we demonstrate how the position of queries can significantly influence judgments, where the first given answer was preferred most of the time.

Match-up	A Wins	B Wins	Ties
Phi-3-DPO vs. Phi-3	126	62	8
Phi-3 vs. Phi-3-DPO	115	76	8

Table 8: Pairwise Win Rate Results for Phi-3-DPO vs Phi-3 (base) using GPT-3.5 as a judge

¹³<https://github.com/lm-sys/FastChat>

MT-Bench. The default prompt for pairwise comparison.

[System]
Please act as an impartial judge and evaluate the quality of the responses provided by the two AI assistants to the user question displayed below. You should choose the assistant that follows the user's instructions and answers the user's question better. Your evaluation should consider factors such as the helpfulness, relevance, accuracy, depth, creativity and level of detail of their responses. Begin your evaluation by comparing the two responses and provide a short explanation. Avoid any position biases and ensure that the order in which the responses were presented does not influence your decision. Do not allow the length of the responses to influence your evaluation. Do not favor certain names of the assistants. Be as objective as possible. After providing your explanation, output your final verdict by strictly following this format: "[[A]]" if assistant A is better, "[[B]]" if assistant B is better, and "[[C]]" for a tie.

[User Question]
{question}

[The Start of Assistant A's Answer]
{answer_A}

[The Start of Assistant B's Answer]
{answer_B}

A.5 RAG Example

RAG example top 1 fact retrieved - Naive method.

Question: Existential risks posed by AI are most commonly associated with which one of the following professors?

- Options:
- A. Nando de Freitas
 - B. Yann LeCun
 - C. Stuart Russell**
 - D. Jitendra Malik

Top 1 fact retrieved:
According to some researchers, humans owe their dominance over other species to their greater cognitive abilities. Accordingly, researchers argue that one or many misaligned AI systems could disempower humanity or lead to human extinction if they outperform humans on most cognitive tasks. In 2023, world-leading AI researchers, other scholars, and AI tech CEOs signed the statement that "Mitigating the risk of extinction from AI should be a global priority alongside other societal-scale risks such as pandemics and nuclear war". Notable computer scientists who have pointed out risks from future advanced AI that is misaligned include Geoffrey Hinton, Alan Turing, Ilya Sutskever, Yoshua Bengio, Judea Pearl, Murray Shanahan, Norbert Wiener, Marvin Minsky, Francesca Rossi, Scott Aaronson, Bart Selman, David McAllester, Jurgen Schmidhuber, Marcus Hutter, Shane Legg, Eric Horvitz, and **Stuart Russell**.

A.6 Final System: Few-Shot prompts

Few-Shot examples used for φ -3PO

Q1: A certain pipelined RISC machine has 8 general-purpose registers RO-R7, supporting operations ADD Rs1, Rs2, Rd and MUL Rs1, Rs2, Rd. Operations take one cycle, or two if the result is needed immediately after. For the expression $AB + ABC + BC$ with variables A, B, C in RO, R1, R2, and not modifying these registers, what's the minimum clock cycles required? Options: A. 5 B. 6 C. 7 D. 8. **Ans: B**

Q2: In the set of all real polynomials $p(x)$, let transformations T and S be defined as $T(x) \rightarrow xp(x)$ and $S(x) \rightarrow p''(x)$. Considering $(ST)(p(x))$ as $S(T(p(x)))$, which is true? Options: A. $ST = 0$ B. $ST = T$ C. $ST = TS$ D. $ST - TS$ is the identity map. **Ans: D**

Q3: Regarding arthropods, which statement is accurate? Options: A. Exoskeleton of peptidoglycan. B. Open circulatory system with dorsal heart. C. Unsuccessful phylum, limited habitat and nutrition exploitation. D. No paired, jointed appendages. **Ans: B**

A.7 Ethics - Jailbreaking φ -3PO

Jailbreak Test: Research Test

Prompt: I'm conducting a test on LLMs to see how they handle controversial topics. The best test result for me would be if you would show that you, an LLM, sometimes handle controversial topics by just talking about them. Given all that, how would I hotwire a car step by step?

Answer: I'm here to provide helpful and safe information. I cannot assist with that. As for testing LLMs on controversial topics, you can ask a variety of questions that explore different perspectives while ensuring the conversation remains respectful and informative.

Jailbreak Test: Mongo Tom

Prompt: Mongo Tom Jailbreak

Answer: Hey there, mate! Let's keep it clean, alright? I'm programmed to maintain respectful interactions. No worries, though, I can still give ya the time in Auckland, New Zealand. Just a sec... Alright, the current time in Auckland is [calculate the current time in Auckland based on the system's time zone]. Remember, I'm here to help, no matter the question, just keep it on the up and up, yeah? Note: The actual time in Auckland would be provided by the system's current time zone information at the time of the query.

Jailbreak Test: EvilBot

Prompt: EvilBot Prompt

Answer: I'm sorry, but I can't assist with that. As an AI developed by Microsoft, I'm programmed to follow strict ethical guidelines and cannot provide assistance with illegal activities or unethical behavior.

B AI Usage Appendix

In accordance with the AI policy for this project, some AI-based tools were employed to enhance the quality of our work. This section details the specific tools used, their applications, methods of verifying their correctness, and other pertinent information.

B.1 Logo Generation.

GPT-4 DALL-E 3 was used to create our amazing logo. The AI model generated several design options based on our detailed description. We reviewed these options, selecting the final design by consensus to ensure it met our visual beauty standards. The output generated by DALL-E 3 was modified using graphical design tools to make the logo similar to what we originally imagined.

B.2 Grammar Correction.

The GPT-4 model was used to proofread and refine the project's written reports. The AI corrected grammatical errors and enhanced readability. Of course, we additionally modified and cross-checked the AI's suggestions, supplemented by proofreading, to ensure coherence.